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Social Inclusion of the Back Ward Classes Women Through Professional Education

¹Dr. K.V. Amarnath & ²M. Kumaraswamy

¹Teaching Assistant and ²Research Scholar

Department of Sociology, Sri Krishnadevaraya University, Ananthapuramu,
Andhra Pradesh, India

ABSTRACT

The Indian Caste system is the unique dimension on which the Indian society is stratified into higher and lower castes with differential access to resources of society. These are Upper classes/ castes: and backward classes/ castes. All cases belonging to the upper class category exercise control over different sources of power (viz. ritual, political and economic power). This paper seeks to examine the progress of Backward Classes Women in Professional Education Particularly Engineering Education in the era of Globalization and the consequent Social Inclusion into the mainstream society. This paper is based on the research study carried out on 310 Girls Students enrolled in the 2 Engineering Colleges of Ananthapuramu of Andhra Pradesh. The paper draws the conclusion that the progress of BC's Girls in Engineering education shows remarkable progress, in the sense that more and more girls from middle and lower middle class BC's girls are getting enrolled into engineering courses and their academic consistency is quite appreciable and today they are brimming with confidence and confidence to take up challenging job career on par with men and women of other communities. The higher education did ensure high degree of social inclusion of the erstwhile socially excluded BC's women to work shoulder to shoulder with others for the development of the nation as well as for their families and their own self.

Keywords: manmade discrimination, caste structure

Introduction

The Indian Caste system is the unique dimension on which the Indian society is stratified into higher and lower castes with differential access to resources of society. These are Upper classes/ castes: and backward classes/ castes. All

cases belonging to the upper class category exercise control over different sources of power (viz. ritual, political and economic power). In one sense, all these castes, which were considered upper in pre- British India were mainly urban and they themselves were sources of ritual and secular power, or were close to these sources. Because of these initial advantages of higher status, they were the first to exploit the modern economic and educational opportunities that opened up during British rule, which the vast majority of the populace, who were mainly rural were deprived of these benefits. The latter remained backward in the traditional social order.

The backward classes of India of contemporary India had their origin from the numerous artisan castes that were part of the societal schema of stratification, in which these castes were only just above the so called Untouchables, whose social duty was to render services to the higher caste with Jajmani obligations in the agrarian society and with relative acceptability in view of the essential nature of their services to the four fold Varnas and the intermediary castes that emerged thereafter through the intermarriages amongst them. The artisan castes, who were at the bottom layer of the depressed castes who were just above the so called untouchables, These castes were considered as backward but not as polluting because of their functional necessity etc for the agrarian society. They were allowed to reside in the vicinity of the village and their entry into the household was permitted when needed. The scheduled castes and the backward classes were socially set apart excluded from power, education and rituals.

The term exclusion means according to Chamber's dictionary to shut out to hinder from participation of or ejection. Social exclusion connotes social denial deprivation or preclusion from participation. This social practice is as old as the hills. It is rooted in the ideology of inequality. It can be the case as well as the consciousness of inequality. It is willed and manmade inequality. Natural inequality is therefore of a different genre and kind. The British regime conducted census in which it was identified that there were about 3,000 castes existent in the country with relative degree purity and pollution devoid of social, economic and political power and remained outside the social orbit. The effort to attain social mobility was dissuaded by the higher castes In other words these backward sections of society were socially, educationally and politically excluded to remain stay put to their traditional jobs.

The inequality that existed between the higher castes and the backward classes continued for generations and the caste occupations continued to be practiced for generations. There was virtual social exclusion of these castes from the resources of society.

The introduction of secular education by the British saw the Sudras, Dalits taking to education at the behest of the British rulers, who for their own reasons, encouraged the downtrodden to take up education, so as to weaken the freedom movement which was taking roots. The Christian missionaries established schools, colleges, teacher training institutes, hospitals as part of their missionary activity, which in a way helped the downtrodden sections to seek opportunities for their social mobility. There were some backward classes who tried to make use of education to attain social mobility.

The British rule introduced egalitarian principle, which was manifest in law and politics. There were services of administration reforms, which gave the backward classes and minority groups increased political power, and economic benefits and educational opportunities, several new avenues for claiming higher status opened up and there was greater scope for pursuing new aspirations. English education became the basis of new employment opportunities, which were free of caste considerations. The National movement also buttressed the egalitarian ideology challenging the hierarchical nature of the caste system.

At the dawn of independence, the priority before the government was to ensure equality of all sections of society. The social inequality that existed from times immemorial in different social segments, of the Indian society, the Scheduled castes, Scheduled Tribes, and the other Backward Castes (broadly known as backward classes) represent the social groups, which suffered through the ages due to caste prejudices, economic inequality, educational backwardness and lagging behind the field of education and economic development in comparison to certain advanced or the forward castes. To minimize the social and economic deprivations, many social provisions were made to safeguard their interests along with the provision of equality before the law and prohibition of discrimination of grounds of race, religion, and caste. The constitutional provisions were made for the upliftment of the weaker sections like the Scheduled Castes and Scheduled Tribes through reservations in educational Institutions and in jobs. It was then thought that, by

providing education to these sections, the social mobility of these sections could be triggered through, educational and occupational mobility. The planning on the earlier years tried to focus on the educational development of these sections, for education has multiplier effect and can propel occupational, social mobility of these sections over a period of time to ensure an egalitarian society..

The term backward class refers to specially, to those backward groups other than SCs and STs. They were referred to as the depressed classes during the British regime. Similarly, some include among backward class those who are far below the upper cluster, some to those who are just above SCs and STs and some refer to middle cluster of caste hierarchy as backwards. Different states of India have their own classification of backward classes in their respective states. The Census of 1951 and the Planning commission of 1951 had estimated OBC population as 20 per cent approximately. According to the Kaka Kalelkar Commission (1953), the total population of the OBCs in India was fixed as 31.8 per cent, where as the Mandal commission (1980) calculated OBC population as 52 per cent.

The state governments were asked to enumerate the backward classes in their respective states and prepare a list of backward classes for which 10 states responded and further 8 states and Union territories notified lists of OBCs for the grant of Post-matric scholarships. It was only in 1977, when the Janata Party that came to power it appointed the Second Backward Classes Commission popularly known as the Mandal commission which submitted its report in 1980. The commission identified 3743 backward castes and recommended 27 per cent of reservations for OBCs in Government service as well as in educational institutions both in centre and in state governments. The Janata government fell and their efforts were shelved by the congress government as their two efforts to place it in the parliament and arrive at a consensus could not yield result.

The emergence of National Front Government in 1989 tried to implement the Mandal commission recommendation in 1990 granting 27 per cent of reservations in government service, which evoked nationwide upheaval. As many as 26 writ petitions were filed in High courts and Supreme courts. It was only in 1992, the apex court upheld the decision of the Government to grant 27 per cent of reservations to Non Creamy Layer OBCs of. It was sequel to this that the National Commission for Backward Classes came into existence

to examine request for inclusion into OBCs. Consequently, Pre-matric, Post-matric scholarships and construction of Hostels for OBC boys and girls took place in 1998. In 1992, National Backward Classes Finance Corporation was set up to provide loans and micro credit facilities.

Backward Classes in Andhra Pradesh: The Government of Andhra Pradesh had drawn a list of Backward Classes and allowed scholarships, reservations in professional colleges and in the government services etc for the uplift of the Backward Classes, which was struck down in the absence of a Commission. Accordingly in April 1968, a commission was appointed to determine the criteria of backwardness and also to prepare a list of backward classes. The commission submitted its report in June, 1970. Accordingly, 92 classes were officially listed as socially and educationally backward and classified them into 4 groups viz. A, B, C, & D and recommended 30 % of seats for OBCs but the Government later fixed the quota as 25 % in professional colleges and also in services.

Education of the backward classes was the priority of the government in the sixties, accordingly starting of schools, provision of hostels were provided to enhance enrollments and retention in the school system both at the primary and secondary levels. The decade of the eighties was devoted to expansion junior colleges, degree colleges to increase enrolments in the higher education. The decade of the nineties and the globalization triggered global job market for our engineering and software professionals resulted in the proliferation of engineering and computer courses which enticed the youth from higher and middle classes of all castes. Higher education now has greater premium and irrespective of social positions, people nurture hopes for their of their wards' prosperous career. India today is a knowledge society selling its professionals to world job market.

Higher Education in Post-Independent India

The present system of Higher Education in India has its roots in Mount Stuart Elphinston's 'minute' of 1823, in which he pressed for establishment of schools for teaching English and the European sciences. The idea of establishing universities in India on the model of London University (i.e., a University of affiliating type) was first given in Sir Charles Wood's dispatch of 1854, which has been described as 'Magnacarta of English Education in India'.

The Universities in India were modeled after London University (1836). Initially the Universities in England were funded from private resources but progressively state funding became dominant as the state became the major beneficiaries of higher education. The first universities in India were set up in 1857 in Bombay, Calcutta and Madras with state funding statutes, for meeting the manpower requirements of the colonial government. Following the government's 1913 Resolution, Universities were started at Banaras (1916) and Patna (1917), almost simultaneously; two Universities, Mysore (1916) and Osmania (1918) were started. Between 1917 and 1919 the whole organization of higher education in India was exhaustively examined by the government's Calcutta University Commission.

From the recommendations of the Commission sprang seven new Universities in ten years, thus at the time of independence, there were about 20 Universities in the country.

After independence, there had been a phenomenal expansion of higher education in India as each year many new Universities and Colleges were established. Efforts were also made to examine the progress made in the field of education. This was carried out in the form of Kothari Commission (1966) which laid great deal of stress on the qualitative improvements in higher education and on linking it with other sectors of society and economy. New Education Policy (NEP) document has expanded on this theme of quality up gradation and character building through higher education. The NEP also emphasizes on cultural dimensions of life and pluralist nature of Indian Education as the diffusion of arts, science, philosophy and literature of Europe and the study of Indian languages. These recommendations were enlarged to include Law, Medicine, and Engineering.

Indian education system had multi-faceted tasks to be executed, namely, meeting the challenge of qualitative and quantitative expansion; strengthening the linkage between education and the labour market and bridging the gap between work and knowledge; reducing the regional disparities; widening socio economic base of education system through programme of protective discrimination as well as of proper incentives so as to reduce, and ultimately eliminate, the differentials between the scheduled and non-scheduled, the rural and the urban as well as the male and female population; transforming the teaching and teaching-oriented education into a learning and learner-oriented

education and to emphasize the creativity of the learner rather than the assimilation of "received" truth; and developing education meaningfully in such a manner that it contributes to national integration, humanism and love for nature.

The era of globalization widened the horizons of higher education, enticing the youth with global employment lucrative career opportunities in software, management. There was a mad rush for technological and management courses. The proliferation of Engineering colleges saw many taking up engineering courses. This has also kindled the quest for engineering career among BC's parents to educate their wards. The earlier quest was to find employment in the other countries but the unprecedented absorption of technological graduates from India in the software industry for their proficiency in English language has sky rocketed the demand for engineering courses. When boys and girls from all communities craved for engineering courses, did the trend in any way entice BC's girls into professional course like engineering?, Whether or not this higher education propelled their social inclusion were the issues this present research study tried to examine.

Objective: This paper seeks to examine the progress of BC's Women in Professional Education Particularly Engineering Education in the era of Globalization and the consequent Social Inclusion into the mainstream society.

Method of Study: This paper is based on the research study carried out on 310 BC's Women Students enrolled in the 2 Engineering Colleges of Ananthapuramu of Andhra Pradesh.

Findings and Discussion

1. The BC's girls enrolled in the 2 engineering colleges of Ananthapurmu District show that they are in the right age. A majority of backward class women students 83.55 per cent of them are in the group of 18-21 years and those who were above 23 were only 3 in number. It is heartening to know that women in their prime age, exhibit enthusiasm and interest to come forward to higher education and attain skills to participate in the process of development. None of them had any break in their academic career.
2. five sub-categories of the backward castes into groups A, B, C, D & E in which BC-A is the most backward and BC-D is the least backward BC-B and BC D form 65.47 per cent of the respondents while among the most backward of BC-A only 21.62 per cent of the respondents could be found.

The higher per cent age of BC-B, BC-A and BC-D category are commensurate with their per cent age in the total population. Which means they are able to enrol into engineering course due to the provision of Backward class reservation. This inclusive policy enabled these BC's girls to find entry into professional course merely due to reservation.

3. The year of study of these girls shows that there has been consistent increase in the enrolment of BC's girls into engineering courses in Ananthapuramu District every year.
4. Another important finding drives home the point that out of the 310 candidates, 67.74 per cent of respondents had bagged the seat by reservation. It was indeed heartening to note that 31.61 per cent of respondents on the sample had bagged the seat in open quota, which is quite creditable. If we analyze further, it can be seen among those who had bagged Engineering seat on open quota the sub castes of BC- B (42.42) and BC- C (45.45%) are more. The point of inference here is that, students belonging to these sub castes have excelled to bag seat in the open quota. It is heartening to note that the girls had also bagged seat in the open merit, which means within short time, these girls could scale higher education on par with girls from other communities. It is an indicator of certain inclusion into the mainstream society. Shut out from exposure to secular education for generations, these girls from this present generation could make the best of the encouragement provided by the parents and the government could register spectacular academic progress in enrolling onto Engineering education to acquire professional education for a lucrative career in engineering to work shoulder to shoulder along with their male counter parts to demonstrate the fact that they are inferior to none.
5. When we glance at their places of birth, 57.10 per cent hail from rural and Semi-Urban background. In spite of the fact that they hail from backward places, it has not hindered their spirit and the enterprise to get engineering education. This also shows the initiative and the change in the mind set of the parents to educate their girl child with the best of education so as to make them as the productive members of the society.

Conclusion

The paper draws the conclusion that the progress of BC's Girls in Engineering education shows remarkable progress, in the sense that more and more girls from middle and lower middle class BC's girls from Rural, Semi-Urban and Urban areas of Ananthapuramu District are getting enrolled into engineering

courses and their academic consistency is quite appreciable and today they are brimming with confidence to take up challenging job career on par with men and women of other communities. Hailing from orthodox, socially excluded BC's community, these girls of the present younger generation are now able to enter Technological Institutions making use of the Inclusive reservations and welfare inputs to register high level of academic performance. Thus higher education certainly did ensure a high degree of social inclusion of the erstwhile socially excluded BC's women to work shoulder to shoulder with men and women of other communities in professions all over the globe experiencing high degree of social inclusion with social parity, confidence and dignity with their religious identity and religiosity remaining intact.

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Table No.1
Distribution of Respondents by Age

Sl. No	Age	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	17	34	10.97
2.	18	64	20.65
3.	19	63	20.32
4.	20	71	22.90
5.	21	61	19.68
6.	22	14	4.51
7.	23	3	0.97
	Total	310	100.00

Table No. 2
Distribution of Respondents by their Sub - Caste

Sl. No.	Category	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	BC-A	67	21.62
2.	BC-B	137	44.19
3.	BC-C	9	2.90
4.	BC-D	66	21.29
5.	BC-E	31	10.00
	Total	310	100.00

Table No. 3
Respondents by their Year of Study in Engineering Course you

Sl. No.	Year of study	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	I	87	28.06
2.	II	63	20.32
3.	III	86	27.75
4.	IV	74	23.87
	Total	310	100.00

Table No. 4
Category under which the respondents got seat

Sl. No.	College Seat	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	Open	98	31.61
2.	Reservation	210	67.74
3.	Management	2	0.65
	Total	310	100.00

Table No. 5
Distribution of Respondents by their Place of birth

Sl. No.	Place of birth	No. of Respondents	Percent
1.	Rural	133	42.90
2.	Semi-Urban	58	18.71
3.	Urban	119	38.39
	Total	310	100.00